

Students' Performance in English and Communication Strategies in Teaching in Congressional District 2, Batangas Province

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Abstract

Communication is a fundamental skill as this is critical not only in students' academic development but also in their future career. However, international tests reveal low language proficiency. This study aimed to determine the level of student performance in terms of language proficiency and academic achievement. This also investigated the extent of utilization of teaching communication strategies in terms of variety, adaptation of technology, and fluency in delivery while also exploring the challenges encountered to be able to craft enhancement activities. This study employed mixed method research design using questionnaire and interview guide as instruments. The sample is composed of 135 secondary school English teachers in the Congressional District II of Batangas Province identified through multi-stage stratified proportionate sampling. Mean, Pearson r , and thematic analysis were used to interpret the data. Students' level of performance in terms of language proficiency and academic achievement is good with grand means of 2.62 and 2.88 respectively. Teachers greatly utilized a variety of strategies and fluency in delivery both with means of 3.59 and moderate extent of adaptation of technology with a mean of 3.25. All teaching communication strategies have a significant relationship with student performance ($p=0.01-0.048$). Teachers experience several challenges in teaching English: students' limited language proficiency; affective and psychological barriers; instructional and resource limitations; and diverse student proficiency and learning contexts. While students have generally good levels of language proficiency and academic achievement, their ability to communicate in written mode and manage academic tasks needs enhancement to further strengthen performance. The proposed enhancement activities were designed to develop students' vocabulary, comprehension, and oral communication skills in meaningful and practical contexts. These activities focus on developing key areas of English language learning while supporting teacher effectiveness. Teachers' adaptation of technology is a priority area which may inform future policy and program implementation.

Keywords: *communication strategies, performance, language, proficiency*

Introduction

Communication is a fundamental skill in the 21st century. Students are honed to be powerful communicators at an early age as this skill is critical in their academic development. Studies revealed that students differ in their communication competence (Al-Sumait et al., 2022; Cao & Sarsenbayeva, 2023; Nadeem & Zabrodska, 2023). There are students who are capable of communicating based on their age level. On the other hand, there are students who lag behind other students when it comes to communicating both in oral and written forms.

The United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4 emphasizes the need for the attainment of quality education. Thus, in the Philippines, Republic Act 10533 or the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 was established which stipulates the use of appropriate instructional strategies and learner-centered curricula. The strategies utilized by teachers are fundamental in facilitating the learning of students. This enables the delivery of quality education which will contribute to national goals for development.

The percentage of 15-year-old students who achieved at least Level 2 reading proficiency ranged from 89 percent in Singapore to 8 percent in Cambodia. Nearly none of the children achieved reading scores at Level 5 or above (OECD average: 7 percent). Based on implicit clues about the information's content or source, these students are able to understand long texts, handle abstract or paradoxical concepts, and distinguish between truth and opinion (OECD, 2021).

This poor result in language proficiency is an alarming situation especially for language teachers. Complete learning, recitation, drill, ice-breaking, memory recall, brainstorming, class discussion, games, listening and reading, paragraph writing, filling-in-the-blanks, English camp, assembly, cooperative learning, problem-based learning, project-based learning, implementation of good habits, and fun English learning are just a few of the teaching strategies that researchers have found. Also, emphasizing academic language, literacy, and vocabulary, connecting background knowledge and culture to learning, encouraging classroom interaction, increasing comprehensible input and language output, and stimulating higher-order thinking skills are also popular. Thus, it is anticipated that the application of successful language teaching techniques will result in new developments for students' success in learning English (Saragih et al., 2023).

This study is anchored on Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) Theory, developed by Hymes (1972) and further elaborated by Canale and Swain (1980); Socio-Cultural Theory proposed by Vygotsky (1978); and the Cognitive Academic Language Learning Approach (CALLA) developed by Chamot and O'Malley (1987). CLT focuses on the capacity to communicate effectively in real contexts as the desired end of language learning. In Socio-Cultural Theory, the "Zone of Proximal Development" (ZPD), is where learners move forward with the assistance of more knowledgeable others (e.g., teachers or peers). The Cognitive Academic Language Learning Approach (CALLA) is a learning model that combines content-area instruction and English language acquisition through the formal teaching of learning strategies.

As an English teacher, the use of strategies in teaching language proficiency is believed to be an important aspect of instruction. However, as shown by international assessments, there has been a problem in achieving a good level of performance. The present study aimed to assess the students' performance in English and the communication strategies in teaching in the Congressional District II, Batangas Province. Based on the findings, the researcher proposed learning activity sheets designed to enhance students' skills in vocabulary and expression, reading comprehension, writing proficiency, motivation, confidence, and the integration of technology in language learning.

This study focused on the following questions:

1. What is the students' level of performance as assessed by teachers in terms of the following factors:
 - 1.1 language proficiency; and
 - 1.2 academic achievement?
2. What is the extent of utilization of communication strategies in teaching relative to:
 - 2.1 variety of strategies;
 - 2.2 adaptation of technology; and
 - 2.3 fluency in delivery?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the assessments on the level of students' performance and on the extent of utilization of communication strategies in teaching?
4. What are the challenges encountered by teachers in teaching the English language?
5. Based on the analysis of the study, what enhancement activities may be proposed?

This study tested the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. There is no significant relationship between students' level of performance as assessed by teachers in terms of language proficiency and academic achievement and the extent of utilization of communication strategies in teaching relative to variety, adaptation of technology, and fluency in delivery.

Materials and Methods

Research Design

This study made use of a mixed method research design. According to George (2025), the goal of mixed methods research is to address research issues by combining aspects of qualitative and quantitative research. Through this design, this study provides a quantitative result on students' level of performance as assessed by teachers as well as the extent of utilization of communication strategies. This was reinforced with the challenges encountered by teachers in teaching language which may not be fully identified through quantitative means only.

Participants

The population of this study is composed of 207 secondary school teachers in the Congressional District II of Batangas Province. From this population, Raosoft sampling calculator with 5 percent margin of error was used to determine the study's sample size. Multi-stage stratified proportionate sampling was employed to determine the number of respondents from each grade level. There was the same sample size for Grade 7, 8, and 10 which is 23. On the other hand, both Grade 9 and 11 have 25 respondents while Grade 12 has 15 participants.

Instruments

The research utilized a self-made questionnaire as the main instrument of the study. Items on the questionnaire were framed based on literature. The first part focused on the level of students' performance in terms of language proficiency and academic achievement. The second part focused on the extent of utilization of teaching communication strategies in terms of variety, adaptation of technology, and fluency in delivery.

A comprehensive and iterative validation process was carried out to guarantee the accuracy, validity, and reliability of the questionnaire. The development of the instrument began with an extensive review of related literature, including books, journals, dissertations, scholarly articles, and interviews relevant to language proficiency and teaching communication strategies. The adviser and external validators with expertise in the field were requested to review the questionnaire to further assess its clarity, relevance, and appropriateness. Suggestions and feedback gathered during the validation process were integrated into the final version of the instrument. To establish the reliability of the questionnaire, Cronbach's alpha was employed.

Interview was conducted to substantiate and enrich the findings of the study. The researcher conducted an in-depth discussion about challenges encountered by teachers in teaching the English language. Through interactions, this method was utilized to share the attitudes, perceptions, knowledge, experiences, and practices of the participants with others.

Procedure

Before starting the study, proper communication was made sure to all stakeholders. To obtain authorization to gather data from schools and carry out the research, a letter was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS). Using online forms, the researcher sent the survey to every respondent. The researcher provided the district supervisor with the link to the online survey. In order to explain, verify, clarify and corroborate the quantitative data, the researcher conducted an interview with at least one teacher per sub-office. Participants shared their knowledge and expertise on the relevant topics discussed, which were communicated prior to the session.

The study adhered to strict ethical standards to protect participants' rights and welfare. All respondents were guaranteed anonymity and confidentiality, with no personally identifiable

information recorded or disclosed in the study results. Informed consent was obtained from each participant prior to participation, and they were assured that their responses would be used solely for research purposes. The researcher ensured transparency, honesty, and respect in all interactions, following the principles of voluntary participation, privacy, and responsible data management throughout the research process.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used to summarize responses. Pearson *r* was used to determine the significant relationship between the assessments on the level of students' performance and on the extent of utilization of communication strategies in teaching.

Results

1. Assessment of the Students' Level of Performance

This study assessed students' level of performance in terms of language proficiency and academic achievement as assessed by their teachers.

1.1 Language Proficiency

The development of students' language proficiency is a fundamental aspect of English instruction which needs to be considered in assessing learning outcomes. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1
Students' Level of Performance in Terms of Language Proficiency

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Students can express thoughts clearly in spoken English during class discussions.	2.73	0.63	Good
2. Students are comfortable speaking English with classmates and teachers.	2.46	0.76	Fair
3. Students can understand spoken instructions in English without repetition.	2.78	0.69	Good
4. Students are able to follow English movies, videos, or lectures without subtitles.	2.84	0.72	Good
5. Students can easily understand English texts read at school.	2.79	0.73	Good
6. Students can summarize what they have read in English in their own words.	2.61	0.76	Good

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
7. Students can write emails or letters in English with correct grammar and vocabulary.	2.39	0.76	Fair
8. Students feel confident when writing essays or reports in English.	2.46	0.77	Fair
9. Students can explain complex ideas in English both orally and in writing.	2.43	0.74	Fair
10. Students can appropriately use formal and informal English depending on the situation.	2.67	0.75	Good
Grand Mean	2.62	—	Good

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Very Good); 2.50-3.49 (Good); 1.5-2.49 (Fair); 1.00-1.49 (Poor)

The results reveal that the students' level of performance in terms of language proficiency was good, with a grand mean of 2.62. The highest scored item is being able to follow English movies, videos, or lectures without subtitles with a mean of 2.84 interpreted as Good. Students can understand spoken instructions in English without needing them repeated with a mean of 2.78 interpreted as Good. Also interpreted as Fair is explaining complex ideas in English both orally and writing with a mean of 2.43.

The students also showed Fair performance in comfortably speaking in English with classmates and teachers with a mean of 2.46. Resting in the middle is the ability to summarize what they have read in English in their own words with a mean of 2.61 interpreted as Good. The lowest scored item is writing emails or letters in English with grammar and vocabulary with a mean of 2.39 interpreted as Fair.

1.2 Academic Achievement

Academic achievement is a key indicator of students' learning outcomes which needs to be considered in evaluating their overall performance. This study assessed the level of students' performance in terms of academic achievement. The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2
Students' Level of Performance in Terms of Academic Achievement

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Students can consistently achieve beyond passing grades in their courses.	2.87	0.63	Good
2. Students complete all assignments on time.	2.89	0.66	Good
3. Students perform well in examinations and quizzes.	2.81	0.63	Good
4. Students understand the material taught in class.	2.99	0.59	Good

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
5. Students meet the academic expectations set by teachers.	2.90	0.59	Good
6. Students can handle the academic workload without feeling overwhelmed.	2.72	0.65	Good
7. Students stay focused during lectures and study sessions.	2.84	0.68	Good
8. Students actively participate in group discussions and projects.	3.01	0.69	Good
Grand Mean	2.88	—	Good

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Very Good); 2.50-3.49 (Good); 1.5-2.49 (Fair); 1.00-1.49 (Poor)

Table 2 shows that students have a good academic achievement with a grand mean of 2.88. Among the items, the highest scored is actively participating in group discussions and projects with a mean of 3.01 interpreted as Good. The next higher scored item is understanding the material taught in class with a mean of 2.99 interpreted as Good. Another higher scored item is meeting academic expectations set by teachers with a mean of 2.90 interpreted as Good. Resting in the middle is completing all assignments in time. The lowest scored item is handling academic workload without feeling overwhelmed with a mean of 2.72 interpreted as Good.

2. Extent of utilization of communication strategies in teaching

The use of effective teaching communication strategies is a vital component of successful instruction which needs to be considered in enhancing student learning. This study assessed the extent of utilization of teaching communication strategies in terms of variety, adaptation of technology, and fluency in delivery.

2.1 Variety of strategies

This study identified the extent on how varied the strategies employed by teachers. The result is presented in Table 3.

Table 3
Extent of Utilization of Teaching Communication Strategies in Terms of Variety of Strategies

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Use discussions, role-plays, and storytelling to support communication.	3.50	0.58	Great Extent
2. Adjust strategies to fit the learners' English levels.	3.64	0.51	Great Extent
3. Allow collaborative learning to support peer	3.70	0.46	Great Extent

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
communication.			
4. Incorporate games or songs to stimulate participation.	3.52	0.57	Great Extent
5. Incorporate cultural references to enhance understanding.	3.35	0.49	Moderate Extent
6. Implement differentiated strategies based on students' needs.	3.60	0.52	Great Extent
7. Encourage student-led questioning and interaction.	3.53	0.57	Great Extent
8. Provide sentence starters to help students express ideas.	3.63	0.54	Great Extent
9. Rephrase content when students do not understand.	3.75	0.49	Great Extent
10. Use questioning techniques to stimulate critical thinking in English.	3.72	0.51	Great Extent
Grand Mean	3.59		Great Extent

Legend:. Scale interpretation: 3.50–4.00 = Great Extent; 2.50–3.49 = Moderate Extent; 1.50–2.49 = Slight Extent; 1.00–1.49 = Least Extent.

Table 3 shows that the teachers employed a variety of strategies to a great extent with a grand mean of 3.59. The highest scored item is rephrasing content when students do not understand with a mean of 3.75. Another higher scored item is using questioning techniques to stimulate critical thinking with a mean of 3.72 interpreted as Great Extent. Allowing collaborative learning to support peer communication was also scored higher with a mean of 3.70.

In the middle is implementing differentiated strategies based on students' needs with a mean of 3.60 interpreted as Great Extent. The lowest scored item is incorporating cultural references to enhance understanding with a mean of 3.35 interpreted as moderate extent.

2.2 Adaptation of Technology

The integration of technology is an essential aspect of modern teaching which needs to be considered in evaluating instructional strategies. This study assessed the strategies employed by teachers in terms of technology adaptation.

Table 4 shows that teachers exhibit a moderate extent of adaptation of technology with a mean of 3.25. The highest scored item is using digital presentations to deliver lessons clearly with a mean of 3.77 interpreted as Great Extent. Integrating educational videos to support concepts with a mean of 3.65 interpreted as Great Extent.

In the middle is sharing digital content for student review with a mean of 3.25. Assigning tasks using online platforms such as LMS and Google Classroom was scored lower with a mean of 2.99 interpreted as Moderate Extent. This means that teachers have limited access to online platforms. Also, utilizing video conferencing tools to extend communication gained a mean of

2.95 interpreted as Moderate Extent. The lowest scored item is using mobile apps such as Quizlet and Kahoot to enhance engagement with a mean of 2.92, interpreted as Moderate Extent.

Table 4
Extent of Utilization of Communication Strategies in Teaching in Terms of Adaptation of Technology

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Use digital presentations to deliver lessons clearly.	3.77	0.44	Great Extent
2. Integrate educational videos to support concepts.	3.65	0.51	Great Extent
3. Assign tasks using online platforms (e.g., LMS, Google Classroom).	2.95	0.89	Moderate Extent
4. Use mobile apps (e.g., Quizlet, Kahoot) to enhance engagement.	2.92	0.84	Moderate Extent
5. Share digital content for student review.	3.25	0.73	Moderate Extent
6. Encourage students to submit digital projects.	3.11	0.80	Moderate Extent
7. Integrate feedback tools (e.g., polls, surveys) into class.	3.05	0.82	Moderate Extent
8. Utilize video conferencing tools to extend communication.	2.99	0.86	Moderate Extent
9. Promote responsible use of social media in English learning.	3.45	0.71	Moderate Extent
10. Monitor students' responsible use of technology for English learning.	3.34	0.69	Moderate Extent
Grand Mean	3.25		Moderate Extent

Legend: Scale interpretation: 3.50–4.00 = Great Extent; 2.50–3.49 = Moderate Extent; 1.50–2.49 = Slight Extent; 1.00–1.49 = Least Extent.

2.3 Fluency in delivery

Fluency in delivery is a critical component of effective teaching as it affects learner comprehension and engagement. This study assessed the strategies employed by teachers in terms of fluency in delivery.

Table 5 shows that the teachers exhibit great fluency in delivery with a mean of 3.59. The highest scored item is emphasizing key points during delivery with a mean of 3.70 interpreted as Great Extent. The second highest scored item is maintaining focus and staying on topic during

delivery with a mean of 3.69 interpreted as Great Extent. Using tone and pitch to emphasize important details was applied to a great extent with a mean of 3.66.

Table 5
Extent of Utilization of Communication Strategies in Teaching in Terms of Fluency in Delivery

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Speak clearly and at a moderate pace during instruction.	3.62	0.57	Great Extent
2. Maintain fluency and coherence when explaining lessons.	3.55	0.60	Great Extent
3. Avoid excessive use of fillers (e.g., “uh,” “like”).	3.25	0.65	Moderate Extent
4. Ensure explanations flow logically.	3.62	0.56	Great Extent
5. Emphasize key points during delivery.	3.70	0.53	Great Extent
6. Adjust speech rate based on student understanding.	3.65	0.57	Great Extent
7. Use tone and pitch to emphasize important details.	3.66	0.59	Great Extent
8. Pause intentionally to allow for comprehension.	3.66	0.56	Great Extent
9. Maintain focus and stay on topic during delivery.	3.69	0.54	Great Extent
10. Manage time effectively while maintaining fluency.	3.55	0.57	Great Extent
Grand Mean	3.59		Great Extent

Legend: Scale interpretation: 3.50–4.00 = Great Extent; 2.50–3.49 = Moderate Extent; 1.50–2.49 = Slight Extent; 1.00–1.49 = Least Extent.

Resting in the middle is adjusting speech rate based on student understanding with a mean of 3.65. Maintaining fluency and coherence attain a mean of 3.55 interpreted as Great Extent. Managing time effectively while maintaining fluency was scored lower with a mean of 3.55. The lowest scored item is avoiding excessive use of fillers with a mean of 3.25 interpreted as Moderate Extent.

3. Relationship between assessments in the Extent of Utilization of Teaching Communication Strategies and Students' Performance

The relationship between the extent of utilization of communication strategies in teaching and on the level of students' performance was determined in this study.

Table 6 presents the relationship between the level of performance in language proficiency and the extent of utilization of communication strategies in teaching. The results

reveal that language proficiency is significantly correlated with all three teaching communication strategies examined.

Table 6
Level of Performance in Language Proficiency and Extent of Utilization of Communication Strategies in Teaching

Teaching Communication Strategies	<i>r</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	Interpretation
Variety of Strategies	0.200	133	.020	Significant
Adaptation of Technology	0.456	133	.001	Significant
Fluency in Delivery	0.171	133	.048	Significant

Legend: *r* = Pearson correlation coefficient. *df* = degrees of freedom. Significance level set at $p < .05$.

Specifically, a significant positive relationship was found between language proficiency and the variety of strategies used by teachers ($r = .200$, $p = .020$). A moderate positive and statistically significant relationship was also observed between language proficiency and the adaptation of technology ($r = .456$, $p = .001$). Lastly, language proficiency showed a significant positive relationship with fluency in delivery ($r = .171$, $p = .048$).

Table 7
Level of Performance in Academic Achievement and the Extent of Utilization of Teaching Communication Strategies

Teaching Communication Strategies	<i>r</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	Interpretation
Variety of Strategies	0.345	133	.001	Significant
Adaptation of Technology	0.445	133	.001	Significant
Fluency in Delivery	0.268	133	.002	Significant

Legend: *r* = Pearson correlation coefficient. *df* = degrees of freedom. Significance level set at $p < .05$.

Table 7 shows the relationship between the level of performance in academic achievement and the extent of utilization of teaching communication strategies. Specifically, a moderate positive and statistically significant correlation was found between academic achievement and the variety of strategies used in teaching ($r = .345$, $p = .001$). Likewise, academic achievement demonstrated a moderate positive and significant relationship with the adaptation of technology ($r = .445$, $p = .001$). In addition, a significant positive relationship was observed between academic achievement and fluency in delivery ($r = .268$, $p = .002$).

Table 8
Relationship between Assessments in the Extent of Utilization of Teaching Communication Strategies and Students' Performance

Teaching Strategies	Communication	r	df	p	Interpretation
Variety of Strategies		0.275	133	.001	Significant
Adaptation of Technology		0.481	133	.001	Significant
Fluency in Delivery		0.224	133	.009	Significant

Legend: r = Pearson correlation coefficient. df = degrees of freedom. Significance level set at $p < .05$.

In terms of variety of strategies, the p -value is 0.001 and the r value is 0.275. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant weak relationship between this strategy and the performance of students. In terms of adaptation technology, the p -value is 0.001 and the r value is 0.275. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

This means that there is a significant moderate relationship between the use of technology and student performance. In terms of fluency in delivery, the p -value is 0.001 and the r value is 0.224. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significantly weak relationship between fluency and student performance.

4. Challenges Encountered

This study determined the challenges encountered by teachers in English instruction. The identification of these challenges was carried out through individual interviews with selected English teachers. The discussion focused on the central question: *What challenges do teachers encounter in teaching English?*

Table 9 presents the challenges encountered by English teachers as reflected in the responses of the participants. The responses were analyzed and grouped into specific challenges and broader themes to provide a clearer understanding of the issues affecting English instruction.

The findings of the study revealed four major themes that describe the challenges encountered by English teachers in instruction. These include Students' Limited Language Proficiency; Affective and Psychological Barriers; Instructional and Resource Limitations; and Diverse Student Proficiency and Learning Contexts.

On students' limited language proficiency, the majority of the respondents emphasized that learners demonstrate weak vocabulary, poor expression skills, and low reading comprehension. These challenges hinder students from effectively communicating their ideas and understanding texts. Teachers observed that learners tend to rely on their first language when expressing themselves, which indicates insufficient exposure to the English language. Furthermore, slow reading and limited comprehension delay learning progress. These findings imply that there is a need to strengthen reading programs and implement strategies that enhance vocabulary development and language use.

In terms of affective and psychological barriers, respondents highlighted that students experience anxiety, lack confidence, and feel uneasy when using English, particularly in speaking tasks. Fear of committing errors discourages active participation in discussions. Moreover, low motivation and short attention span negatively affect students' engagement in learning activities. These results suggest that emotional and psychological factors play a crucial role in language learning, and teachers need to create a supportive, encouraging, and engaging classroom environment.

With regard to instructional and resource limitations, teachers reported a lack of adequate teaching and learning materials, which affects the effectiveness of instruction. Limited access to books and digital resources constrains both teaching strategies and student learning opportunities. Additionally, teachers encounter difficulties in preparing appropriate lessons and assessments due to diverse learner needs and time constraints. This indicates the need for increased institutional support, provision of instructional materials, and continuous professional development for teachers.

Table 9
Thematic Analysis on the Challenges Encountered by English Teachers

Responses	Challenges	Theme
<i>"Lack of confidence to explain their ideas/opinion probably due to weak vocabulary skills."</i> <i>"Difficulty in expressing thoughts because of their vocabulary is limited."</i> <i>"Students are having difficulty communicating using English..."</i> <i>"Students find it difficult to express thoughts clearly..."</i>	Poor Vocabulary and Expression Skills	Students' Limited Language Proficiency
<i>"Inability to comprehend articles due to lack of exposure to reading."</i> <i>"They lack comprehension skills including reading/literacy."</i> <i>"Poor reading comprehension..."</i> <i>"Struggle to understand basic vocabulary..."</i>	Low Reading Comprehension and Fluency	Students' Limited Language Proficiency
<i>"Learners tend to feel uneasy explaining complex ideas in English..."</i> <i>"Students aren't comfortable in using the English language."</i>	Lack of Confidence and Uneasiness	Affective and Psychological Barriers
<i>"Underdeveloped English skills, lack of motivation..."</i>	Low Motivation and Attention Issues	Affective and Psychological Barriers
<i>"Lack of resources with appropriate learning materials."</i> <i>"Learners... lack learning materials."</i>	Inadequate Teaching and Learning Materials	Instructional and Resource Limitations
<i>"It is a huge task for teachers to prepare materials..."</i>	Difficulty in Lesson	Instructional and

Responses	Challenges	Theme
<i>"Diverse levels of language proficiency..."</i>	Preparation and Assessment Varying Levels of Language Proficiency	Resource Limitations Diverse Student Proficiency and Learning Contexts
<i>"Limited understanding of reading English text..."</i>	Limited Understanding of English as a Second Language	Diverse Student Proficiency and Learning Contexts

On diverse student proficiency and learning contexts, respondents noted that variation in students' language proficiency adds complexity to instruction. Learners come from different linguistic, socio-cultural, and educational backgrounds, resulting in uneven levels of understanding. Some students require more assistance in comprehending spoken and written English. These differences highlight the importance of differentiated instruction and the use of contextualized teaching approaches to address diverse learning needs.

5. Proposed Enhancement Activities

The proposed enhancement activities are designed to develop students' vocabulary, comprehension, and oral communication skills in meaningful and practical contexts. These activities focus on developing key areas of English language learning while supporting teacher effectiveness. Vocabulary development is enhanced through context-clue exercises, word detective tasks, and digital word maps. Reading comprehension is strengthened with short passages, story mapping, and guided reading exercises that promote understanding and analysis of texts. Writing skills are developed through paragraph building, editing tasks, sentence-to-paragraph exercises, and narrative or descriptive writing, fostering clarity, coherence, and proper language use. Oral communication and confidence are cultivated through presentations, show-and-tell sessions, role-playing, and peer discussions. Technology-enhanced learning incorporates digital tools for collaborative projects, interactive activities, and story mapping, adapting instruction to diverse learner needs. Finally, teacher capacity building focuses on innovative teaching strategies, effective communication techniques, and the integration of technology to create motivating, inclusive, and impactful English lessons.

Discussion

Students understood English well, but their skills in spoken and written English were not that strong. The result, which showed that the students were not able to attain the highest level, may have been attributed to their limited exposure to language use and practice. Gamboa et al. (2021) argued that even though everyone had the opportunity to learn the language, some people were still having trouble using it in writing or speaking. Others still have low or poor English language skills despite all the efforts. Students have met the necessary criteria for learning while noting that the students did not actually meet the highest level, which signifies the need for

improvement. This may be attributed to instructional competence of teachers which led students to attain the required competencies. Academic performance is the knowledge that students acquire and is evaluated by a teacher using grades and/or educational objectives that students and teachers establish to be met during a given time frame. Other stages of higher and tertiary education are significantly impacted by secondary school students' performance (Ibrahim & Maude, 2022).

Teachers have been prioritizing the use of diverse strategies to cater to the needs of students. This may be because of the mandate of the department to apply various techniques to help students learn while considering their own interests and needs. Teachers are connecting with the students and considering their level of competence when designing lesson tasks and materials. This may be attributed to the aim of education to make learning inclusive and that no child will be left behind. In relation, Eslit et al. (2024) mentioned that teachers demonstrated resilience and adaptation through professional development, flexible teaching methods, and technological integration.

The use of technology in English instruction is not much popular among teachers possibly due to some limitations. This may be attributed to the limited internet access, unavailability of devices, and limited training for teachers to use advanced technologies. Teachers present lessons with coherence. This may be attributed to the experience and competence of teachers in their professional work. According Wolf et al. (2023), professional development is highly desired in order to enhance comprehension of the language requirements in the standards.

Teachers with higher language proficiency tend to employ a wider range of communication strategies in teaching. Although the correlation is weak, it suggests that improvements in language proficiency are associated with increased strategic variation. Teachers with higher language proficiency are more likely to effectively integrate and adapt technological tools as part of their communication strategies during instruction. Lastly, greater language proficiency contributes to more fluent and effective instructional delivery.

Higher levels of academic achievement are associated with the use of a wider range of communication strategies in instructional delivery. Teachers with higher academic achievement tend to more effectively integrate technological tools as part of their teaching communication strategies. Higher academic achievement contributes to clearer and more fluent instructional delivery.

Variety of learning experiences can address the varying needs of learners and thereby improve learning outcomes. Student engagement is enhanced when teachers employ technology in their teaching. Competence of teachers can transpire to students. Faez et al. (2022) argued that teachers' language skills only explain a small portion of the variance in self-efficacy, indicating that although language skills are crucial, self-efficacy is more complex than language competency alone.

Students' limited language proficiency is a challenge. Learners demonstrate weak vocabulary, poor expression skills, and low reading comprehension. These challenges hinder students from effectively communicating their ideas and understanding texts. Affective and psychological barriers are also a challenge. With regard to instructional and resource limitations, teachers reported a lack of adequate teaching and learning materials, which affects the effectiveness of instruction. On diverse student proficiency and learning contexts, respondents noted that variation in students' language proficiency adds complexity to instruction.

Conclusion

Students demonstrate a generally good level of language proficiency and academic achievement. Teachers employ a great variety of strategies. Students' language proficiency and academic achievement is affected by teachers' use of communication strategies. Technology adaptation has the greatest impact, while variety of strategies and fluency in delivery shows weaker but significant associations. Higher teacher competence and language proficiency contribute to better student performance.

Teachers face several challenges in teaching English that affect student learning. A major challenge is students' limited language skills, including weak vocabulary, poor reading comprehension, and difficulty expressing ideas, which make communication harder. Students also experience low motivation, lack of confidence, and anxiety, which reduce their participation. Teachers struggle with limited resources, insufficient teaching materials, and little time to prepare lessons that meet diverse student needs. In addition, differences in students' language ability and cultural backgrounds make teaching more complex, requiring personalized strategies.

To improve English learning outcomes, enhancement activities should focus on strengthening reading, writing, vocabulary, and grammar skills; increasing student engagement and motivation; integrating technology; and supporting teacher professional growth. Similar studies may be conducted on a wider scale focusing on other areas of language learning.

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